

Bypassing state non-compliance: the case of Slovenia

ABSTRACT: Bypassing state non-compliance: the case of Slovenia

Keywords: anti-money laundering, data flow, state non-compliance, transactions, smurfing, bank accounts, money instruments, transfers

Purpose

After the ambitious issuance of the EU 849/15 (4th AML) directive to make transactions and ownership more transparent and query effective, member states had to adopt and issue new domestic laws on anti-money laundering and terrorism financing. The Financial Intelligence Unit (FIU) of Slovenia follows a high degree of transparency in publishing suspicious transactions; however, its effective use is extremely unfriendly if a member of the public wishes to obtain meaningful statistics and draw conclusions from the published data. The main point of this paper is to propose an effective European anti-money laundering (AML) system that will facilitate international investigations using Slovenia and an ongoing investigation of smurfing as an example of potential state non-compliance with the EU AML 4th and 5th directives and how to bypass them in case communications channels have leaks and suspicious activity is not recognised and raised on an international level by state authorities.

Design/methodology/approach

A comparative approach to European directives on AML is used and explores how the implementation of the supervisory rights has affected the Slovenian FIU and implemented within the Slovenian legal system. Basic statistics are used when evaluating the suspicious activity report (SAR) transactions published by the Slovenian FIU, which were reported by obliged entities in 2018. Moreover, a school-like example

of smurfing activity is presented for recognising the inefficacy of a member state authority.

Findings

Inefficacy of data transfer and investigations data retrieval processes within the intrastate investigations is shown to be of great concern. Moreover, the need for a centralised AML authority should be taken into consideration to expedite and increase security to protect the European financial system from allowing criminal money into circulation or letting single member states be a source of money transfers to different state systems. The analysis has shown an estimate of more than 1 billion euros worth of transactions being reported in 2018 and published at the Slovene FIU website for the public to explore.

Originality/Value

The article investigates the data flow for criminal investigations regarding the EU AML 5th directive and exposes its weaknesses in cases of state non-compliance when access to bank account holders is subject to an international investigation. Moreover, it suggests a better approach to allow EU competent authorities to have an international overview within all member states bank account holders to bypass inefficient and time-consuming queries with single member state dependence.

Crime knows no border

The proposal dated 19 April 2018 for the 5th AML directive of the European Parliament and of the Council extends the AML scope and lays down rules to facilitate the use of financial and other information for the prevention, detection, investigation or prosecution of money laundering, predicate offences, financing of terrorism and serious crimes with a generalised framework for member states to follow. However, with the lack of state supervision on the EU level, the framework cannot be optimised for better information gathering and in case of state non-compliance and poor domestic legal framework, member states can bypass proper reporting and oversee financial transactions misconduct.

The updated version of the 5th AML directive issued in 2018 sets clear guidelines to member states to implement a system that will be limiting in capacity to support money obtained from criminal activities that freely circulates within the global monetary system. As criminal conduct is global, loopholes in the current system need to be exploited to devalue and prevent intrastate flow of monetary means with a criminal source. Intense exploitation of each member state legislation has to take into account the whole realm of globalised crime. As crime knows no borders, the same must apply for information sharing related to suspicious (SAR) transactions and information on bank account holders to facilitate investigations and the freezing of assets when sparse beyond national borders.

Even though the update to the 4th AML directive aims at facilitating data transfer of bank account holders, in its core aim it only sets guidelines and leaves an increased amount of manoeuvrable space to member states to release financial information and financial analysis for a globalised view of financial activity of businesses operations and personal account holders. When an investigative red flag comes from a non-EU country, due to loose time limits of answering requests from member states, funds can be transferred and hidden due to inadequate access to financial intelligence data among European competent authorities with a globalised overview of financial crime activity.

The obligation for member states to establish a bank account ownership register is a step closer in visualising transaction activity and automation of SAR reporting. The proposal to update the 4th AML directive adds a new set of entities who will obtain access within a member state to query and freeze financial assets. As it stands with granting access to bank account holder information within a member state, the EU

framework shall also grant direct access to European agencies with analytical capabilities and sufficient expertise to expedite between member states investigations accounting for data protection laws and provide a more thorough EU-wide picture of account holders and transaction activities.

International organisations and European Architecture

The globalised phenomenon of using the financial system for money laundering purposes and financing of terrorism invoked a response from the international community in establishing an intergovernmental organisation founded in 1989 on the initiative of the G7 called the Financial Action Task Force (FATF)². The task force has no authority nor does it conduct criminal investigations, but it sets recommendations for the international community to follow to revise the legal framework to protect the global financial system from the abuse of money laundering activities and financing of terrorism. Among other initiatives, the recommendations include:

- Implementation of relevant international conventions,
- Criminalisation of money laundering,
- Authorisation for authorities to confiscate the proceeds of money laundering,
- Implementation of customer due diligence, record keeping and SAR reporting requirements for financial institutions and designated non-financial businesses and professionals, and
- The establishment of financial intelligence units (FIU) to receive and disseminate SAR reports.

The recommendations within the European Union member states are being implemented through the EU AML directives, with updates arising on justifiable time intervals. The implementation period is a tedious process, taking many years to come into effect within domestic legislations, leaving the member state the only responsible entity of its enforcement. As was noted, fines arising within the European banks on money-laundering violations “have underlined the serious shortcomings of the European Union AML regime (Kirschenbaum, 2018)”. Moreover, “AML supervision of banks and other firms rests largely with the national authorities of individual EU member states, in increasing tension with the legal framework for centralised prudential supervision within the euro area and the European single market (Kirschenbaum, 2018)”. Lack of superior supervision leaves member states’

2 <http://www.fatf-gafi.org/about/membersandobservers>

investigations liable to political influence and regulatory oversight of AML practices within financial institutions being exploited by illicit financial practices taking advantage of the weak link.

An enquiry to the Slovene FIU about ongoing and finished AML breach investigations resulted in an e-mail response, where a total of 164 inspections (2017: 3, 2018: 70 and up till today in 2019: 91) were conducted. The FIU noted that up to the last legislative review, no entities were ever controlled on the AML breaches before the FIU acquired its powers and it directed its attention to the control of accountants, tax advisors, and business entities who offer business and fidelity services. The FIU noted that on two occasions a fine was issued, but since the process is not yet legally binding, they cannot disclose further information on the subject. While AML breaches within the banking sector occurred in many EU member states, no such breach can be found in the public domain for the Slovene banking sector. Is it due to lack of control or do all the banks have an implacable AML system?

Data communication

The goal of the 5th AML directive to establish a bank account register within a national central bank of a member state facilitates the knowledge base of where the funds are located; however, it gives the sole power and responsibility to the member state. Although member states are obliged to provide a yearly statistics report to the European Commission (EC), such data is not exhaustive to the EU executive body to obtain a better image of how FIU, competent authorities and obliged entities are dealing with enquiries to the register. The EC shall also be informed of enquiry lawfulness and admissibility check by a data protection officer, whose mandate of operation is again left to the member state to decide.

Figure 1: Data access flow to bank account holders

Granting independence and trust from EU authority oversight shall be taken into consideration to allow state autonomy; however, as the legislative state structure in the Republic of Slovenia calls for more EU involvement and restriction within the field of anti-money laundering and the terrorism financing domain, the need for a centralised superior supervisory body is imminent. As shown in Figure 1, the communication path from outside the member state domain is only strictly defined from a foreign FIU. The domestic authority is obliged to respond, but gives no assurance for log activity monitoring and the time frame of 10 days when extreme cases occur is too long³.

A more problematic data limit communication path is the indirect access from Europol and Europol national units. Taking into consideration that a high-profile international investigation is brought to the attention of Europol, the no response time limit on queries requests to both communicating parties that is tied to a domestic FIU shall raise investigation efficacy concerns. High-level state corruption may interfere with international investigations for asset freezing and asset recovery when politically exposed persons (PEP) and their business associates are the subject of investigative inquiries if the establishing EU prosecutor, whose investigative court is not located in the member state, and can result in poor evidence collection given the framework that the 5th AML directive is trying to establish.

Moreover, the content to which the member state must ensure a reply on inquiries related to bank account holders for Europol, is defined in Article 10 as “duly justified requests” and “within the limits of its responsibilities and for the performance of its tasks”. Although, data privacy is of concern, Article 10 does not guarantee a full reply and the directive mandates too strict conditions for an analytically sophisticated agency of the European Union in bringing severe financial misconduct to justice in a more effective way. This raises the question of who will guarantee proper transaction information obtained on a subject in question from financial institutions that keep a record of bank activity when a high level of state non-compliance and inefficacy to initiate criminal investigations with EU directives is part of state politics and its legal framework?

4th AML directive implementation

In October 2016, the Republic of Slovenia passed into law a new version of the act on anti-money laundering and financing of terrorism answering the EU directive 841/15.

3 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32018L0843>

With such a manoeuvre, it showed the EU counterpart a strong will in updating its own legislative framework to be in harmony with EU 841/15. However, when a member of the general public digs deeper into the new legal framework focusing Article 68 of the ZPPFT-1⁴, which deals with SAR reporting, one encounters its 6th point that states: “the Minister of Finance can issue special guidelines to customers or businesses to not have to report cash transactions defined in point 1 of the same Article”. Inquiries were sent to the Ministry of Finance and the FIU initiated a public debate regarding the issue at hand related to which business entities may be excused from cash SAR reporting. EU 849/15 clearly states that auditors, representatives of legal profession and tax auditors may be excused by obliged entities from cash SAR reporting in settings of a criminal investigation. Another excused entity is clearly described in Article 4, which is extremely limited in set rules and amount of money turnover.

After the public call, the Ministry of Finance noted that a business has been excused from guidelines; however, on 8 March 2018 the new public document on the same topic was issued. The legislative body of the Republic of Slovenia shall have removed such power from the Ministry of Finance, a manoeuvre which is not mentioned anywhere in the EU 849/15 directive, and issued another more controversial document instead, granting more entities the opportunity to not have cash transactions reported by obliged entities. When a list is being issued and authorised by the Minister, is this, as mentioned by EU directive 849/15, sent forward to the EC to approve the entities not having SAR reports filed on them?

SAR reporting

In its second paragraph, Article 68 of the ZPPDFT-1 lists obliged entities (banks, savings banks, payments institutions, post offices and organisers of gambling) to report to the FIU any transaction above EUR 15,000 that is wired to countries:

1. that are listed as high-risk countries with strategical insufficiencies where adequate measures are not in force for prevention and detection of money laundering and financing of terrorism, or,
2. where there exists a high likelihood for occurrence of money laundering and financing of terrorism.

A maximum of one day later, the reported data is published in an Excel worksheet on

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Zakon o preprečevanju pranja denarja in financiranju terorizma (ZPPDFT-1)

the FIU website⁵. Although some degree of transparency is achieved, the published data is not precise or exhaustive, and is limited in scope and extremely user unfriendly to a member of the general public trying to obtain meaningful statistics from the dataset. Injustice is done to businesses, who conduct legitimate business operations with countries listed as high-risk entities where money laundering or financing of terrorism may occur. With such practice, the FIU places an additional unnecessary burden on obliged entities, deceives legitimate business operations and provides foreign business contact information to the general public.

SAR reporting provides a new dimension for the prevention and investigation of financial crime. As noted, “SAR presents an additional cost to the affected institutions, it has no doubt changed the way crime is being investigated, it is a paradigm shift from prosecution and punishment to interruption, disruption and confiscation of proceeds of crime (Johnson, 2019).” Moreover, “SAR is useful for developing financial intelligence to investigate and detect abuse and misconduct, although it is feared that it may be abused by the state as a tool for infringing the right to privacy of citizens (Johnson, 2019).” The SAR implementation shows two positive options; on the one hand, another tool to bring financial criminals to justice by gathering financial intelligence from an external source, and on the other, putting pressure on obliged entities to implement an automatised system for the detection of SAR and bypass its liability for non-compliance with regulatory obligations. With a sophisticated system and a third-eye inspection, detecting tax evasions and money laundering becomes a more effective method.

Data reported by obliged entities from 2018

The data set for 2018 consists of 16,636 reported transactions, starting from the 3 January 2018 and ending with 27 December 2018. Most of the transactions were carried out in EUR and USD throughout the year. Monthly density transaction reporting is stable throughout the year. On three occasions, there is no client data recorded in the data set, totalling roughly EUR 92,000. On 12 occasions, no data for the client receiving the funds was recorded, totalling roughly EUR 460,000. The highest recorded transaction in 2018 was EUR 9,240 sent from a business located in Slovenia to a business located in Indonesia; the data set records funds were sent to Slovenia. In this circumstance, relying on the definition from the second paragraph of Article 68, as the

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http://www.uppd.gov.si/si/delovna_podrocja/objavljeni_posamezni_vsebinski_sklopi/objave_38_clen_z_ppdft/podatki_o_transakcijah_38_clen_zppdft/

data shows a money transfer within Slovenia, what was the basis of the obliged entity to report such transaction as a non-ordinary one? The data set also contains the lowest transaction of EUR 0, perhaps an entry mistake performed by the data set administrators. The total reported transaction turnover of money transferred to high-risk countries for 2018 totalled roughly EUR 1,079,376,000. As the number presents a significant amount, a number of questions arise: how much of these funds were actually pursued for an international investigation; how much was laundered or used for terrorism financing and finally, how much was actually exposed when legitimate business practices were performed and were discriminated by the legal requirement? Since the ZPPDFT-1 law holds for the Republic of Slovenia, it is safe to assume that only Slovenian obliged entities report transactions to the FIU. A data set recorded business headquarters address registration in 22 different countries, most registered in Slovenia, followed by the United Kingdom (8 clients) and the USA (6 clients). As reported directly by the FIU, transactions move to 75 different countries of which 22 are within the European Union and 53 outside of the EU. The same issue emerges again: how is it possible that a transaction that is wired within the European Union emerges as suspicious and is among countries listed as high risk for money laundering and the financing of terrorism? However, the data set also lists the address of the client who is receiving the transfer and, on several occasions, it does not match the data field of where the money was transferred to. In this instance, the complexity of business operations and its bank accounts are sparse and due to restricted investigative practices, difficult to investigate and prosecute.

Case study

An organisation based in the Republic of Slovenia and listed in the UPPD transactions data file in 2018 conducted an international business operation of product delivery from outside and within the European Union to Italy. The Italian customer paid for all the products by cash, where the price of one truck of product totalled roughly EUR 20,000 and the turnover of delivery trucks was around 40 trucks per month. Cash was deposited on a weekly frequency in Slovene banks and the money was later wired to the producer of the product under the label of a paid invoice.

Figure 2: International business operation - case study

Through the Slovene tax office, the company exhibited an internal tax review to organise and deliver the documentation regarding the business operations. The Slovene tax investigator has only the authority to obtain the documentation of business operations within Slovenia. An inquiry to obtain the relevant documentation of business operations from Italy was sent to the Guardia di Finanza, who retrieved the documentation from the accounting firm where an Italian organisation conducting the business was registered. A witness testified on the basis of the knowledge of business operations but never delivered any documentation to the inquiring Italian tax inspection as it was demanded from their side.

Several months later, a truck delivering the product was stopped by the Italian authorities, initiating a criminal investigation of roughly EUR 7 million in cash transferred across borders of the European Union. Despite the awareness of the Slovene tax office of the increased circulation of cash between borders, no steps were taken by the Slovene authorities to initiate a criminal investigation, consequently raising a contention of inefficacy to share pertinent data within international tax reviews and investigations. Not only is the data retrieval a lengthy process, but it also shows a lack of authority on the part of the Italian authorities to obtain pertinent data when the business operation exceeds the national borders even within the European Union with an air distance of a criminal act within a 40 km air radius.

Conclusion

Since crime knows no borders, the same should hold true for tax authorities and international investigations. The case study showed the inefficacy of the intrastate

documentation retrieval to bring serious financial offences to justice. As long as a financial operation is spread among 2 member state countries, before the authorities make a note and take action, a year has already passed and the criminals are gone from their business operations base, making evidence collection that will stand up in court nearly impossible.

The AML 5 Directive mandates member states to design a database of bank account holders. The accessibility of the data source does not allow direct access from European competent authorities to access data in real time to expedite investigations and data retrievals.

In 2018, in the Republic of Slovenia alone, 1 billion euros worth of transactions were reported to the FIU that were flagged by competent financial institutions as SARs. Even though the data set adds to the concept of transparency, justice is not done to companies that are flagged and controlled even though they are conducting a legitimate business operation. The main question arises, how many of the reported transactions were actually investigated, as we have seen from the case study that a different member state had to step in to initiate a criminal investigation?

Decentralisation and autonomy of member states to be the sole responsible entity to initiate a criminal investigation leads to undiscovered financial crime operations and money laundering. Due to the inefficient current system without an AML centralised supervisor on the EU level, effective protection of the financial system against money laundering operations and financing of terrorism is a state in the European Union that must be addressed and implemented to best serve its citizens.

Notes:

1. Directive (EU) 2015/849 on preventing the use of the financial system for money laundering or terrorist financing (4th Anti-Money Laundering Directive), OJ L 141, 5.6.2015, p. 73–117
2. Directive (EU) 2018/843 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 amending Directive (EU) 2015/849 on the prevention of the use of the financial system for the purposes of money laundering or terrorist financing, and amending Directives 2009/138/EC and 2013/36/EU, OJ L 156, 19.6.2018, p. 43–74
3. Regulation (EU) 2015/847 on information on the payer accompanying transfers of funds – makes fund transfers more transparent, thereby helping law enforcement authorities to track down terrorists and criminals, OJ L 141, 5.6.2015, p. 1–18
4. Uradni List (2016), “Zakon o preprečevanju pranja denarja in financiranja terorizma (ZPPDFT-1)”, st 68/2016, 4.11.2016, p. 9391

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